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PRDM1 activates Ddx17, an Xist-interacting helicase.

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We describe PRDM1 regulation of an Xist interacting helicase, DDX17, which itself was sufficient to control aspects of the oncogenic program. The data support a role for PRDM family molecules in transformation, provide additional evidence for a dominant contribution of the Xist imprinting system in transformation, and provide enhanced detail describing nuclear processes which serve as the molecular basis for transformation in humans (cancer). Helicase control of transformation-associated homeoboxes has not yet been described.

1 **Results**

2 Figure 1: PRDM1 activates Ddx17 helicase.

3 GSE157206
4 GSE233342

5 Figure 2: Ddx17 is an Xist interacting protein.

6 Figure 3: Rad51 depletion activates Ddx17.

7 GSE54266

8 Figure 4: Ddx17 depletion activates PRDM1.

9 GSE173292

10 Figure 5: Ddx17 depletion associated with PRDM1 mobilization results in induction of DUXAP homeobox
11 transcription factors, nuclear factors that occupy specific positions in the hierarchy of homeobox factors
12 that execute transformation resulting in ECT2 induction.

12 GSE173292

13 Figure 6: Ddx17 depletion mobilizes imprinting machinery, influences genomic stability, and activates and
14 represses molecules with transformation potential.

- 15 a. SLX1A and SLX1B expression was lost.
16 b. Dzip3 expression was lost.
17 c. Ssbp3 expression was lost.
18 d. Smarcd1 and SS18 were activated.
19 e. SLBP expression was lost.
20 f. RIG-I was activated.

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